

BMF CP118: Environmental Values Consideration, Information Quality, and Solar Energy Adoption in the United States

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“In the age of information, things are buzzing all over the Earth. Humans have abundant information to keep them entertained all day, and even in The Bird Village, there is excitement in the air.”

—In “Titles of Nobility,” [Wild Wise Weird](#) (2024)

1. Project description

1.1. Main objectives

The current study is conducted to examine the following research questions:

- How is the consideration of environmental value in appliance, technology, and home modification decision-making associated with the willingness to adopt solar energy?
- Is the relationship between the consideration of environmental value in appliance, technology, and home modification decision-making, and willingness to adopt solar energy, conditional on the information quality that they received?

Findings from this study are expected to contribute to promoting the eco-surplus culture and sustainable development [1].

1.2. Materials

The Granular Interaction Thinking Theory (GITT) will be employed for the conceptual development of this study, while the Bayesian Mindsponge Framework (BMF) analytics will be utilized for statistical analysis [2,3]. The dataset comprises responses from 9919 U.S. residents of single-family and small multifamily homes [4]. Statistical analyses will be conducted using the bayesvl R package, which utilizes the Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) algorithm for estimation [5].

For the sake of research transparency and reducing research and reproducibility costs, we have stored all data and computer code on Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/16409983>.

1.3. Main findings

The preliminary analysis suggests that useful and relevant information can enhance the positive association between environmental value consideration and adoption willingness. When the information is relevant but not useful, the moderating effect is also positive, albeit with a lower magnitude (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: The estimated posterior distributions.

2. Collaboration procedure

Portal users should follow these steps to register to participate in this research project:

1. Create an account on the website (preferably using an institutional email).
2. Comment your name, affiliation, and your desired role in the project below this post.
3. Patiently wait for the formal agreement on the project from the AISDL mentor.

If you have further inquiries, please contact us at aisdl_team@mindsponge.info

If you have been invited to join the project by an AISDL member, you are still encouraged to follow the above formal steps.

All the resources for conducting and writing the research manuscript will be distributed upon project participation.

AISDL mentor for this project: **Minh-Hoang Nguyen**.

AISDL members who have joined this project: **Quan-Hoang Vuong, Viet-Phuong La**.

The research project strictly adheres to scientific integrity standards, including authorship rights and obligations, without incurring an economic burden at participants' expenses.

References

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[3] Vuong QH, Nguyen MH, La VP. (2022). *The mindsponge and BMF analytics for innovative thinking in social sciences and humanities*. Walter de Gruyter GmbH. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/8367405102/>

[4] Fuentes TL, et al. (2025). A dataset for understanding self-reported patterns influencing residential energy decisions. *Scientific Data*, **12**, 1273. <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41597-025-05335-8>

[5] Vuong QH, La VP. (2025). Package 'bayesvl' version 1.0.0. <https://books.google.com/books/about?id=znleEQAAQBAJ>

[6] Vuong QH. (2024). *Wild Wise Weird*. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/BOBG2NNHY6>

